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D1.4 – Ethics Report, Y2

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
DEP	Digital Europe Programme
DPA	Data Processing Agreement
EC	European Commission
EIA	Ethical Impact Assessment
EU	European Union
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
The Consortium Project's Partners	All the Project Partners, viz. TU DELFT + EAAE + ICF + IW
The Project Beneficiaries	The signatory Partners of the Grant Agreement, viz. TU DELFT + EAAE + ICF + IW
TWG	Thematic Working Groups
Y1	Year 1 of the DigiNEB.eu project, i.e., October 2022 – September 2023
Y2	Year 2 of the DigiNEB.eu project, i.e., October 2023 – September 2024

Keywords

Data management; privacy; ethics; privacy policy; data processing roles.

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Executive Summary

The current document, Ethics Report Y2, details the ethical considerations related to the second year of the DigiNEB project. Following a change in the partnership of the project in September 2023, the Project Partners' aim for the second year has been to continue to map and showcase the digital solutions relevant to the stakeholders of New European Bauhaus (NEB) and facilitate community- and network-building while addressing ethical and legal concerns related to re-use of third-party materials and further minimising the processing of personal data.

The report discusses the changes made to various sections of the DigiNEB.eu website following input on ethical and legal aspects from the Project Partners as well as the Ethics Advisor, Prof. Dr. Paolo Balboni, in relation to Ethics Report Y1 from the first year of the project.

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● 1 Introduction

The present document constitutes a follow-up deliverable to Ethics Report Y1, a deliverable highlighting relevant considerations regarding ethics and data protection as well as intellectual property legislation for the initial version of the DigiNEB.eu project website.

A number of changes have taken place in the Project's internal structure in the second half of the Project's duration, resulting in numerous changes in terms of project coordination and management, as well as the management and development of the DigiNEB online platform. The present deliverable, Ethics Report Y2, provides an overview the changes that have been made in the Project and, specifically, the DigiNEB.eu website, and highlights the implications of these changes on the legal and ethical considerations for the project.

○ 1.2 Document structure

This document is an update of the Y1 report and follows a similar setup with that exception the we introduce first the context and outline of the adopted ethics approach:

Section 2 provides the context and the outline of the ethics approach.

Section 3 provides an overview of the questions related to Intellectual Property aspects, specifically regarding concerns related to displaying/re-using materials of third parties on the website that were highlighted in Ethics Report Y1.

Section 4 addresses changes that were made in the DigiNEB with regard to processing of personal data via the DigiNEB website, and the impact these changes have on previously expressed concerns regarding data protection and GDPR compliance.

Section 5 – provides final considerations and recommendations beyond the end of the project.

Section 6 concludes the report.

● 2. Context and outline of the ethics approach

The coordinator of DigiNEB, TU Delft, is a publicly funded Dutch institute of higher education. As such, the coordinator is bound by the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and its own TU Delft Code of Conduct.

The Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity provides researchers with guidelines for their day-to-day activities in practice. The code of conduct has been adopted by all Dutch universities.

The TU Delft Code of Conduct helps staff members, students, and guests to act in line with the values that it considers important, even in complex situations. (Both documents are attached as annexes.)

Open Science

TU Delft is a strong advocate of Open Science. Open Science covers, in this context, Open Access, Open Publishing, Open Education, FAIR Data and Software, Citizen Science, and Open Hardware.

CSA

Considering that DigiNEB is a coordination and support action (CSA), an ethics approach should strongly emphasise how to share information (including private data) and how to interact during (online) meetings.

Working from these three perspectives, we undertook a review in year two, particularly of the online platform where all activities culminate.

We concluded that in the transfer of responsibilities of the platform to TU Delft, we could improve in a number of aspects:

- Avoid the use of material that is potentially copyright protected.
- Remove potentially copyright protected material as much as possible.
- Make all content open using a Creative Commons licence.
- Remove obstacles to information by cutting out the need for registration and removing unnecessary intermediate steps.
- Refrain from gathering personal data if not strictly necessary.
- Only display basic personal data.
- Not store personal data that is not publicly available.
- Reduce the storage of personal data by instead linking to professional profiles of individuals.
- Not share personal data with other parties.
- Not share personal data for purposes other than the DigiNEB project, even within the partnership.
- Ensure equal representation in all groups based on mutual respect.
- Expect all participants to be open to constructive feedback and criticism.

In general

The web platform prefers linking to solutions and tools that are free or open, without being too strict about that. However, we avoid listing the obvious proprietary solutions developed by Microsoft, Apple, Adobe, Google, or Autodesk. Their products are already well known, so there is little need to include them in a platform which aims to support the discovery of tools and solutions.

Because the platform links to many external sites, we explicitly avoid referring to xenophobic, sexist, homophobic, or other intolerant content.

The platform is published under a CC-BY 4.0 licence.

○ 2.1 Terms of Use (web platform)

The purpose of the digiNEB.eu website is to inform visitors about available digital solutions, tools, and projects relevant to the New European Bauhaus (NEB) movement. The website aims to map and showcase digital technologies as well as publicise relevant news and events, thereby fostering a community of cooperation between NEB and ICT stakeholders. By visiting the website and using its services, you are agreeing to the Terms of Use below.

Licensing

The content of the website adheres to the principles of open access and is licenced under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC BY 4.0). This means that you can:

Share — copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format for any purpose, even commercially.

Adapt — remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially. Admin rights to reject or remove content: The website admin retains the right to remove content that does not abide with the Terms of Use of DigiNEB.eu.

Submitting and publishing content

If you provide content to be included in the website you need to declare that you own and/or are legally licenced to publish the content, and that you agree to that DigiNEB.eu make this content available under a CC BY 4.0 license.

Anti-discrimination and harassment policy:

DigiNEB avoids publishing xenophobic, sexist, homophobic or any other intolerant content.

External hyperlinks and services:

The DigiNEB website contains a number of external hyperlinks, intended as an additional service for visitors to the website. DigiNEB excludes all liability for any damage incurred by users of the TU Delft website as a result of visiting another website via an external hyperlink.

○ 2.2 Privacy policy (web platform)

DigiNEB.eu avoids to collect personal data unless it is strictly necessary. It handles the personal data of the visitors to its website with utmost care. Please read more about when and how digiNEB.eu processes personal data in our Privacy Policy.

Cookies

DigiNEB.eu uses only one cookie that facilitates the use of the admin panel in the back office.

Intellectual property

DigiNEB makes a reasonable effort to respect the rights of the legitimate owners of digital text and images on their use. However, this may be impossible in some cases, because one or more of the legitimate owners of the intellectual property or their heirs cannot be traced. If, in your opinion, any text or digital objects published by DigiNEB infringes your rights, you can contact neby@dignebeu.eu. Your e-mail should contain the title of the relevant item, the communication channel and the materials involved. In such cases, DigiNEB will amend or remove the materials, if no other agreement can be reached. A note to this effect will be included in the materials concerned. This

website has been developed for educational and social purposes and not for profit. For this reason, no payment will be made for materials submitted for publication or references on the website. DigiNEB accepts no liability for the inappropriate use of this website or any damage that may arise as a result of its use.

Privacy

DigiNEB.eu only processes personal data when necessary, and takes the utmost care to do so within the law, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). This Privacy Policy provides you with information about the purposes for which digiNEB.eu processes personal data and about exercising your privacy rights.

What personal data does digiNEB.eu process?

DigiNEB.eu seeks to minimise the personal data that is processed and shared: please see below for an overview of personal data that may be processed and stored:

- name
- e-mail address
- affiliation (name of institution or organisation)
- title (prof., dr., ing.)
- additional details provided by the user
- profile picture

DigiNEB.eu aims to only collect the personal data necessary to provide its services and discourages users from submitting unnecessary personal data.

DigiNEB.eu doesn't gather sensitive personal data nor special categories of personal data (i.e., data concerning racial or ethnic origin; political, religious, or philosophical beliefs; trade union membership; genetic or biometric data; data concerning a person's sex life or sexual orientation) are processed.

What are the legal bases for processing personal data?

The legal bases for processing personal data include: Informed consent of the data subject
Processing of personal data being necessary for the performance or contract

How long is the personal data retained?

DigiNEB.eu stores your personal data in accordance with the GDPR.

What are your privacy rights?

You have the right to request access to and rectify the personal data we process about you, as well as to request that the personal data are removed. If you wish to exercise these rights, please contact nebby@dignebeu.eu. DigiNEB will not process your data, move your data to another site or share your data with other parties. You also always have the option to submit complaint about the use of your personal data to the Dutch Data Protection Authority.

Privacy policy for third parties

The DigiNEB.eu website includes hyperlinks to other websites that are not part of DigiNEB.eu. DigiNEB.eu has no responsibility for the way in which these parties process personal data and therefore advises you to inform yourself of these parties' privacy policies or to contact them for a more detailed explanation of their policy on the use of personal data.

● 3 Intellectual Property Considerations

○ 3.1 Overview

Since change of partnership of the DigiNEB project in September 2023, efforts have been made to minimise the Intellectual Property concerns previously identified in the Project. These concerns were generally related to information about third-party tools available on the previous DigiNEB website (see Ethics Report Y1, Section 2). On the updated DigiNEB.eu website, the Digital Innovation tab provides an overview of different types of content relevant to the New European Bauhaus Community.

○ 3.2 Digital Innovation

The front page of DigiNEB as well as the Digital Innovation¹ page both highlight the four different types of DigiNEB initiatives, i.e., Digital Tools, Digital Projects, e-Learning, and Open Licences. The innovations are made accessible to visitors on two different levels: separately via either overviews or keyword and tag search, or through collections of related tools and services. Additionally, visitors can visit the All Directories² page for an overview of all DigiNEB directories and the taxonomy used. There is no need to register, login or provide otherwise personal data to get access to the project's results.

■ 3.2.1 Digital Tools

The Digital Tools³ section of the website is a revised version of what was previously referred to as the Digital Toolkit (see Ethics Report, Y1: 2.2). Similarly, to the Digital Toolkit, the aim of the Digital Tools is to present an overview of sources for software, tutorials, applications, and various other materials that are useful for architects, designers, and communities. Taking into consideration concerns related to copyright infringement, that were previously expressed with regard to the Digital Toolkit, the updated Digital Tools section has been revised to minimise the use or display of content owned by third parties through the following means:

- The main Digital Tools page links to eight third-party websites where digital tools, software, and applications are listed, i.e., ArchitizerTech, B.Green Handbook, Datascape, Democracy Technologies, DigiPedia, Food4Rhino, Mobility Data Space, and Osarch. Hyperlinks redirect the visitors directly to the third-party websites. As advised in Ethics Report Y1 (Section 2.2.1), the Terms of Use of DigiNEB.eu have been updated to indicate that DigiNEB is not responsible any potential damage incurred by users as a result of visiting third-party websites.

¹ <https://digiNEB.eu/digital-innovation>

² <https://digiNEB.eu/digital-innovation/all-directories>

³ <https://digiNEB.eu/digital-innovation/digital-tools>

- The overview/listing of Digital Tools⁴ only displays the name of the tool, as well as a short description and relevant keywords, alongside a hyperlink that redirects the visitor directly to the website of the third party (i.e., owner of the tool). No pictures, images, or other third-party materials are displayed on the Digital Tools overview page, thereby limiting concerns regarding copyright infringement of such materials.

Unlike in the previous version of the Digital Toolkit, external parties can no longer upload content to the Digital Tools page: this addresses earlier concerns about the external parties holding the rights/authorisations for uploading content, and DigiNEB's potential liability in cases where uploads would infringe on any third-party copyrights.

■ 3.2.2 Digital Projects

The previous version of the DigiNEB.eu project website hosted what was considered a news section presenting solutions used in industry or related research domains. This section of the website has been replaced by the Digital Projects⁵ section, which presents databases with projects that develop digital tools or innovations relevant for the New European Bauhaus community. As for Digital Tools, the Digital Projects page highlights third-party collections of digital tools (currently the European Construction Technology Platform, RI.SE, and Digital Built Britain). Additionally, the Digital Projects Directly allows visitors to search among all featured projects using keywords and tags. Hyperlinks take the visitors directly to third-party websites, limiting concerns regarding re-use of copyrighted materials such as logos.

■ 3.2.3 e-Learning

The e-Learning⁶ section has been revised significantly from the earlier version. Initially Trust-IT had set up a Moodle LMS installation that was not fit for purpose. In the new setup the DigiNEB website no longer contains any internal platform on which courses are hosted: rather, the e-Learning page exclusively links to third-party websites with training modules and courses, described as “e-Learning Collections”. Currently, the collections featured are BSI courses and training, EDX Sustainability & Architecture, DeZeen, EU Citizen Science, Rise Educations, Kaggle, Learn Visual Programming, Morphocode Academy, RISE educations, the Material Way, and Woodigital. We have listed these collections explicitly to avoid duplicating (and competing with) good initiatives that already exist within the community.

By not hosting courses internally on the platform, the DigiNEB project seeks to eliminate the personal data of visitors that would need to be processed through registration on the platform, as well as reduce concerns regarding impinging on third parties' rights in relation to any educational materials uploaded to the Project platform or distributed by the Project

⁴ [https://digiNEB.eu/digital-innovation/ outputs/digital-tools-listing](https://digiNEB.eu/digital-innovation/outputs/digital-tools-listing)

⁵ <https://digiNEB.eu/digital-innovation/digital-projects>

⁶ <https://digiNEB.eu/digital-innovation/e-learning>

(see Ethics Report Y1, 2.2.3). Furthermore, no materials such as logos of the third parties are displayed: hyperlinks take visitors directly to the website of the e-Learning platforms.

■ 3.2.4 Open Licences

The DigiNEB.eu platform has introduced a new Open Licences⁷ section, which highlights a collection of external sources with information about open licences for data and code, currently the Open-Source Initiative, Open Definition, and Creative Commons. Below the collections, individual data and software licences are listed and linked. As for the Digital Tools, Digital Projects, and e-Learning pages, the Open Licences section only contains the external websites' names and a brief description as well as keywords, with hyperlinks redirecting visitors directly to the third-party sites.

○ 3.3 New European Bauhaus

To support the community of the New European Bauhaus (NEB)⁸, the DigiNEB.eu website has also been expanded with a collection of information of various NEB projects and initiatives. The NEB drop-down menu features NEB initiatives in four categories: NEB Lighthouse⁹ projects, NEB prizes¹⁰, EIT Enhance NEB¹¹ activities, and NEB Labs¹². Brief descriptions of the various NEB projects and activities are provided, with hyperlinks redirecting the visitor to the projects' websites.

○ 3.4 Other IPR Considerations

As indicated in previous project materials, the Project website and materials produced and owned by the DigiNEB project are made available under the Creative Commons Attribution ([CC-BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)) International licence.

⁷ <https://digiNEB.eu/digital-innovation/open-licences>

⁸ <https://digiNEB.eu/NEB>

⁹ <https://digiNEB.eu/NEB/lighthouses>

¹⁰ <https://digiNEB.eu/NEB/NEB-prizes>

¹¹ <https://digiNEB.eu/NEB/eit>

¹² <https://digiNEB.eu/NEB/NEB-lab>

● 4 Data Protection & Privacy

○ 4.1 Overview

The initial iteration of the DigiNEB platform incorporated a number of approaches and activities that would involve the processing of personal data¹³ of users in a number of different ways. Consequently, Ethics Report Y1, Section 3, highlighted the principles of the General Data Protection Regulation (“GDPR”) that needed to be taken into consideration data processing activities intended to take place within the Project. Following changes in project management, however, decisions have been made to limit potential personal data processing activities to an absolute minimum. The following sections highlight the changes that have been made to the DigiNEB website to eliminate the potential of processing personal data where it is not strictly necessary, or, where personal data processing is necessary, either comply with the GDPR principles.

■ 4.1.1 User registration

Previously users were required to register and to create an account on the DigiNEB.eu website in order to submit content, to access links to e-learning activities, or sign up for the newsletter. In the updated version of the website, users no longer have to register to do so. A newsletter no longer provided: instead, the news is featured on a dedicated page¹⁴ on the website. As a result, the feature allowing users to register and create accounts has been removed, thereby eliminating concerns related to personal data processing for standard users.

Note that the original setup of the platform was based on a so-called “Soft Opt-in” in which users that had registered on platforms of other projects could be imported in the next platform like DigiNEB. A Soft Opt-in is in conflict with EU rules and regulations.

If, in the future, the DigiNEB platform will be expanded to once again allow users to register, the principles of data minimisation will be applied, i.e. only the data needed for the purpose of registering is collected. Optional fields with additional information, which were previously available for users to fill in (see Ethics Report Y1: 3.2), will not be included, thus limiting any risks related to processing unnecessary personal data.

■ 4.1.2 Early Adopters

The DigiNEB website contains a drop-down menu with information about the various parties involved in the project; previously, this section of the website was referred to as the

¹³Article 4(1) GDPR defines personal data as “any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person”.

¹⁴ <https://digineb.eu/news>

'Network', but it has been renamed simply 'DigiNEB'. In the drop-down menu, the four partners EAAE, ICF, InnovaWood, and TU Delft are presented.

Additionally, the drop-down menu has sections for so-called Early Adopters, as well as the External Advisory Board (see Section 3.1.3).

On the DigiNEB platform, an initial group of so-called "Early Adopters" are still presented with their profiles, including name, profile picture, affiliation, and a biographical text: the Privacy Policy highlights the categories of personal data processed from Early Adopters and Editorial Advisory Board members who are featured on the platform. No new individuals are added to that overview.

■ 4.1.3 External Advisory Board

The External Advisory Board (EAB) is made of prominent experts in relevant areas who offer guidance to the project. The members of the EAB have backgrounds across creative industries, accessibility, architecture, design and construction materials. Information on the board members is provided by the members themselves and doesn't contain specific personal data like email addresses, real world addresses or phone numbers. A link to their organisation's website is provided, but not to a personal page within that website.

○ 4.2 Data Protection concerning e-Learning modules

The services related to the e-Learning possibilities highlighted on the DigiNEB.eu project site have been updated in the second half of the project. Ethics Report Y1 (Section 3.5) highlighted need for the Privacy Policy to reflect all relevant data processing activities carried out in relation to users needing to register to access courses (hosted both internally and externally), as well as users being able to upload e-Learning content. Since updated to the DigiNEB website has resulted in the removal of the registration option for users, there are no remaining concerns regarding processing of personal data related to creating an account. Furthermore, as visitors are not able to upload content to the updated DigiNEB website, no concerns related to personal data processing are identified.

○ 4.3 Data Protection and Digital Tools, Projects, and Events

In Ethics Report Y1 (Sections 3.8), concerns about potential data protection issues in relation to users submitting entries to the Digital Tools and Digital Projects were highlighted, namely that users would need to be advised not to post personal data of others, and be informed of their liability if doing so. Following updates to the DigiNEB platform, however, users are able to suggest tools or projects but these are not automatically posted on the website. The description of projects and tools are kept to a minimum. The form doesn't ask for or provide space for sharing private data on individuals. If somehow sensitive information is suggested, such information will be eliminated from the posting. Therefore, the project team does not foresee any data protection concerns related to this.

Ethics Report Y1 (Section 3.7) also highlighted concerns related to potential user registration for webinars or events hosted by the Project on the website. Currently, no event registration is made available via the DigiNEB website, and thus no personal data of visitors is collected for this purpose. If, in the future, DigiNEB events will be advertised and registration offered directly from the DigiNeb website, personal data entered for the purpose of registration will be strictly limited to the information that is necessary to provide the service, as per the advice in Ethics Report Y1 (p. 26).

- 4.4 Podcasts and other sound recordings

Podcasts and other sound recordings represent a new data type that was not addressed in the previous ethics report. All interviewees were invited to participate in a conversation with the podcast host. By participating they were fully aware that the interview was going to be used for a podcast. Because of the potential for words being taken out of context, the editing presents a new layer of production that required consent. The podcast host created an online consent form for all participants to agree on the use of the edited material, and this has been completed by the interviewees. In the case of other recordings explicit consent was gathered beforehand.

- 4.5 Additional data protection considerations

- 4.5.1 Data processing relationships with third-parties

Soundcloud

The web platform uses the services of Soundcloud to store and disseminate the audio files of the podcasts. Soundcloud allows users to integrate customisable players and embedded versions of the Soundcloud waveform player (“Widget”) on third-party sites: see their Terms of Use¹⁵. No information other than the name of the interviewee was provided to Soundcloud. A clear advantage of using Soundcloud is that the embedded material doesn’t import external cookies into the platform.

Cloudflare

Cloudflare is used for content delivery and to improve the security and resilience of the platform. It is a protective layer.

¹⁵ <https://soundcloud.com/terms-of-use>

- **4.5.2 Data processing relationship among Project Partners**

No Joint Controllership Agreement was implemented. All data on the web platform is in the public domain. No additional data is kept in the back office.

- **4.5.3 Transfer of personal data outside of the European Economic Area**

The web platform itself is stored on a server in the Amsterdam area, well within the European Economic Area. No personal data is placed outside the EEA.

- **4.5.4 Cookies**

The current CMS (Grav) creates only one cookie that is used by the admin plugin. This plugin is only used by those who work on the website in the backend.

● 5 Further Recommendations

In the new setup of the web platform the partnership has decided upon a new direction. All information that is organised to the benefit of the New European Bauhaus community (and other users) is freely available without a requirement to register and sharing personal data.

All information is provided openly on the platform. In the back office there is no data on projects, initiatives, tools or persons, other than what is published publicly.

In the previous releases, significant amounts of text and images were taken from the source websites and included in dedicated pages on tools or projects. These in between pages were taken out, avoiding potential copyright infringement and drastically simplifying the maintenance of the platform.

This direction has two important advantages. The DigiNEB website no longer scrapes personal data and users have more direct access to the information they are looking for.

Any steps that the platform will make after the end of the DigiNEB project (31.12.2024) should likewise honour this new approach.

● 6 Conclusions

The consortium took the advice and warnings from the first Ethical Report to heart. It completed a total overhaul of the platform with the aim of eliminating the use of personal data, to be true to the concept of Open Science and to make accessing information easier.

- Annexes

Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity

TU Delft Code of Conduct

